

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 11

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 541 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti rektori
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, p.f.f.d., (PhD), Buxoro muhandislik-texnologiya instituti rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Hududiy ta'lim muassasalari va markazlar bo'yicha prorektor v.b.
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TDIUprofessor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d., TSUE professori
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, f.f.d. profesor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Cham Tat Huei, (PhD) USCI universiteti professori, Malayziya
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d.,(PhD) "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d.,(PhD) TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Djudi Smetana, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dotsenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Krissi Lyuis, p.f.n., Pitsburg davlat universiteti dotsenti, Pittsburgh, Kansas, AQSH
Ali Kopak (Али Кўнак), i.f.d., prof., Karabuk universiteti dotsenti, Turkiya
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, i.f.n., "LUKOIL-Energoservis" Kompaniyasi iqtisodchisi, Moskva.
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., (PhD) TDIU dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Oqil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjaevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, DSc, Prof., Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Rae Kwon Chung, honorary professor of TSUE, Nobel laureate, South Korea,

Osman Mesten, member of the Turkish Parliament, head of the Turkey-Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, DSc, Prof., Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich CSc, Prof., Rector of Academy of Labor and Social Relations

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, DSc, Prof., TSUE Vice-Rector for Scientific Affairs and Innovation

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhritdinovich, DSc, Prof., Rector of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna, PhD, Rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, DSc, Prof., acting Vice-rector for regional educational institutions and centers of TSUE

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, CSc, Prof., of TSUE

Slizovsky Dimitriy Yegorovich, DSc, Prof., of the People's Friendship University of Russia

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, DSc, Prof., Rector of International "Nordic" University

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja ugli, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of the DGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the DCECGPO of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganievich, DSc, Prof., of TSUE

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, PhD in Philology, Professor.

Shoira Azimovna Musaeva, professor of SamDu IS Institute

Cham Tat Huei, PhD, professor at USCI University, Malaysia

Buzrukhanov Sarvarkhan Munavvarkhanovich, DSc, Deputy Minister of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, PhD, deputy of executive director of the "El-yurt umidi" fund

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, PhD, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

Judy Smetana CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Chrissy Lewis CSc, Associate Professor, Pittsburgh State University, Pittsburgh, Kansas, USA

Ali Konak DSc, Prof., Associate Professor of Karabuk University, Turkey

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, CSc, economist at LUKOIL-Energoservis Company, Moscow.

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, associate professor of TSUE

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, doctoral student at Ankara University, Turkey

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, independent researcher of TSUE

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, p.f.f.d., (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich – Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich – Doctor of Philosophy, Professor at TSUE
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich – Doctor of Philosophy, Professor at TSUE
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich – Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor at TSUA
Rustamov Ilhomiddin – Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor at Fergana State University
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich – Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor at TSUE
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna – Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor at TSUE
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Associate Professor at Alfraganus University
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Associate Professor at TSUE
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi – Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor at TSUE
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna – Senior Lecturer at TSUE
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna – Independent Researcher at TSUE

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Iqtisodiyotning pul mablag'lari bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	16
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Yusupov Muxammadali Soxib o'g'li	
Driving economic growth through service exports.....	20
Rahimov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida jamoat tashkilotlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirishda jahon tajribasi.....	27
Raxmonov Abduxalil Rasulovich	
Raqamli marketing va mijozlar bilan ishlashning yangi usullari.....	31
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
Soliq tushumlarini shakllantirish ko'rsatkichlari asosida soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari	35
Jo'raev Husan	
Bevosita soliqqa tortish darajasini ko'paytirish omillari.....	41
Qodirov Baxodir Qudratovich	
Tijorat banklarining xo'jalik subyektlari bilan amalga oshiriladigan muddatli valyuta operatsiyalarini rivojlantirish	47
Ibodullaeva Ma'rifat To'liqin qizi	
Tovarlarning monopol yuqori (past) narxlarini aniqlashni takomillashtirish masalalari	52
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
Bojxona faoliyatini transformatsiyalashda innovatsion boshqaruvni takomillashtirishga oid xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	59
Ro'ziboyev Muhiddin Xushnudovich	
Harnessing foreign direct investment for sustainable economic growth in Central Asia: policy challenges and opportunities.....	63
Mukhammedova Azizakhon Ikromjon kizi	
Mintaqa innovatsion faoliyatida tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	68
Sapayeva N.K.	
Examining Uzbekistan's foreign trade indicators	72
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
Yo'l bo'yidagi xizmat ko'rsatish infratuzilmasini baholash: xizmat sifati va transport xavfsizligini oshirish.....	78
Egamberduyev Odil Buriboyevich	
Роль инноваций в гибком управлении проектами.....	82
Касимова Наима Жахангировна	
Sug'urta bozorini tartibga solishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	87
Tursunova Maftuna Agzamovna	
Mintaqada turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda madaniy turizm resurslarining o'rni va roli	91
Ro'zmetov Baxodir Shomurotovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarining kapital bozorida emission faolligini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari	97
Shodmonova Munisa Nizamjon qizi	
Korxonaning tashqi bozorga chiqishida marketing strategiyasining samaradorligini baholash.....	104
Akramov Bo'ribek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatini boshqarish	110
Saipova Dilnoza Shuxratovna	

Xalqaro standartlar asosida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	114
Egamberdieva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Investitsiyalar samaradorligini baholash va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	120
Jo'raev Paxlavonjon Usarovich	
Soliq qarzdorliklarini yuzaga kelishining ilmiy nazariy asoslari tadqiqi	127
Ostonaqulov Alisher Abdurashidovich	
Korxonalarni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularga imtiyozlar berishni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	132
Z.T. Mirzayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalarda raqamli marketingning ahamiyati.....	139
M.Vohobjonova	
Положение электронной коммерции на международном и национальном уровнях	142
Абдуганиев Учкун Хабибулла угли, Орифбоев Озод Азатович	
Korporativ resurslardan samarali foydalanish orqali kichik biznes subyektlarini barqaror rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish.....	148
Jalolova Muazzamxon Akbarjonovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida kartoshka ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi.....	151
Avazmurodov Islom Nusratullo o'g'li, Muratov Shukrullo Abduraimovich	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati bo'yicha logistik muammolar va ularni bartaraf etishning samarali yechimlari	155
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan sohasida inson kapitali konsepsiyasining amalga oshish bosqichlari yo'nalishlari.....	159
Nasretdinova Aziza Adxamjonovna , Bozarov Elyor Boboqulovich	
Влияние цифровой валюты центральных банков (CBDC) на международную торговлю и финансовые отношения: Анализ и перспективы	164
Номозали Хайдаров	
Raqamli transformatsiya va tadbirkorlik: kichik biznes uchun yangi imkoniyatlar va chora-tadbirlar	167
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich, TDIU magistranti	
O'zbekiston respublikasida aholini samarali ish bilan ta'minlash istiqbollari.....	172
Raxmatullayeva Shahnoza Xamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchxon Sadriddin qizi	
Aylanma mablag'lar aylanuvchanligini tezlashtirishning asosiy yo'llari	179
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Mintaqada to'qimachilik sanoatining iqtisodiy holati tahlili (Xorazm viloyati misolida)	185
Xudoyorova M.O	
Мировой опыт стратегического управления финансовыми ресурсами акционерных обществ.....	190
Абдалиев Айдос Бахтиярович	
Sug'urta faoliyatida axborot jarayonlarini vtomatlashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	196
Shakirov O'tkirbek Taxirovich	
Yerlardan maqsadli foydalanishni aniqlash uslubi.....	199
Yunusov Begench Mavlanberdievich	
Iqtisodiyotda real sektorning ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi.....	204
Amirqulov Umarali Akram o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni baholash amaliyoti va indikatorlari	208
Feruz Raxmatova Yusupjanovna	
O'zbekistonda korxonalarni boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan qo'llash yo'nalishlari	213
Qo'chqorov Tohir Safarovich, To'ychiyev Akmaljon Abdulatif o'g'li	

Agroklasterning tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati	219
Qurbonov Alisher Boboqulovich	
“Yashil” Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda turizmga investitsiyalarning roli	224
Azimov Olimjon Orifovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida aholini ro‘yxatga olish jarayonlarini samarali tashkil etish	236
Annazarova Barno Rustamovna	
Qishloq xo‘jaligida sug‘oriladigan yerlar unumdorligini oshirishni iqtisodiy rag‘batlantirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	242
Isaxanov Muslimjon Ma‘rifjon o‘g‘li	
Logistika va uning sanoat mahsulot ishlab chiqarish tannarxiga ta‘sirini kamaytirish	246
Zokirjonov Asadbek Otabek o‘g‘li	
Sug‘urta kompaniyalari moliyaviy risklarini baholash	249
Baymuratova Gulirayxon Tursunbaevna	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyati tushunchasining rivojlanish bosqichlari	255
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o‘g‘li	
Qishloqlarning resurs salohiyati iqtisodiy kategoriya va iqtisodiyotning agrar sektorini rivojlantirishning zaruriy sharti sifatida	260
Tursunpo‘latov Farxodjon Xoshimjon o‘g‘li	
Kommunal xizmatlarni rivojlantirishda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish.....	265
Mardanova Mohidil Otabek qizi	
Analysis of factors affecting the sustainable development of transport networks in Khorezm	269
Karimboev Dilshod Davronbek o‘g‘li	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy boshqaruv tizimini tashkiliy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	274
Lutfullo Xalimovich Qadirov	
Использование социальных сетей как инструмента маркетинга для фермеров	278
Назарова Гулрух Умаржоновна	
O‘zbekiston transport-logistika tizimida logistika samaradorligi indeksi (LPI) va uning tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatidagi ahamiyati	283
Ismoilov Narimonjon No‘monjon o‘g‘li	
Davlat maqsadli dasturlarini imtiyozli kreditlash tizimining mamlakat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o‘rni.....	287
Shodiyev Shuhrat Sunnat o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekistonda potensial YaIM.ning ekonometrik tahlili	293
Djabbarov Raximjon Abdullaevich	
Tibbiyot muassasalarini kafolatlangan tibbiy xizmatlar paketi asosida moliyalashtirish tizimini takomillashtirish masalalari	298
Muxammadiev Ramz Zoirjon o‘g‘li	
Стратегии развития медицинских организаций в Узбекистане	313
Исломбек Умиров	
Kambag‘allikka qarshi kurashning falsafiy va ijtimoiy asoslari: Tarixiy tahlil	321
Iloxomjonov Jaxongir Alisher o‘g‘li	
Innovatsion loyihalar va startaplarni moliyalashtirishda venchur fondlarining ahamiyati.....	329
Atamuradov Sherzod Akramovich	
Reforms in higher education institutions of the republic of uzbekistan	334
Gafurov Anvar Bazarbayevich	
Namangan viloyati qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining faoliyati samaradorligini ta‘minlash holati va tahlili	343
Ibrogimov Sherzodbek Xalimjon o‘g‘li	

Increasing the innovation potential of construction materials industry enterprises.....	350
Kurbanova Shaxnoza Yuldashbayevna	
Jahon savdo tashkiloti doirasida to'qimachilik mahsulotlarining xalqaro savdosi.....	356
Nurbojev Jaloliddin Mamadiyevich, Abduvohidov Behzod	
Farg'ona vodiysida turizm xizmatlarining rivojlanish tendensiyalari tahlili.....	361
Mamatqulov Zarifbek Sharifjonovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligida investitsiya faoliyatini moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari.....	366
Ko'chqarov Fayzullo Abdujabborovich	
Tarkibiy o'zgarishlar sharoitlarida xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda investitsiyalarni faollashtirish.....	376
M.J.Nabiyeva	
O'zbekistonda aholi omonatlari va ularni kafolatlash tizimi.....	382
Xakimov Zohid Norbo'tayevich	
Взаимодействие образования и бизнеса с элементами дуального образования.....	389
Баходурова Сулхия Азизхожаевна, Акрамова Зарринахон Башировна, Ли Марина Рудольфовна, Ромашкин Роман Анатольевич, Мухтарова Доната Равшанбековна	
O'zbekistonda yashirin iqtisodiyot darajasini qisqartirishda samarali yondoshuv.....	396
Bobojonov Azimjon Akmal o'g'li	
To'qimachilik sanoati korxonalarida innovatsion rivojlanish strategiyalarini takomillashtirish zaruriyati.....	403
Sarimsaqov Doniyor Xomidovich	
Xorazm viloyatida hududiy ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish darajasini baholash.....	409
Madraximov Kaxramon Egamberganovich	
O'zbekistonda aholini uy-joy bilan ta'minlashdagi murakkabliklar va ularning yechimlari.....	414
Xannarov Komiljon Karimovich	
Elektron hukumatdan smart hukumatga.....	419
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznesni rivojlanishi va samaradorligining nazariy-uslubiy asoslar.....	426
Axatova Shaxnoza	
O'zbekistonda banklar faoliyatini tartibga solishning zamonaviy mexanizmlari.....	432
Abdullaev Suyun Artikovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya va hududlarning inklyuziv iqtisodiy o'sishini ta'minlash yo'llari.....	436
Zokirova Bahora Zokir qizi	
Market research strategies in the global tech industry: a comparative study of apple, samsung, and huawei.....	440
Abbos Ruzmamatov	
Strategic analysis of innovation development in manufacturing enterprises: approaches, challenges, and future perspectives.....	444
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Kichik biznes subyektlarini raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda moliyalashtirish texnologiyasi.....	452
Axmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich	
Boshqarish jarayonlarini samaradorligini oshirish orqali iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlash.....	459
Xo'jamurodov Asqarjon Jalolovich, Usmonov Suxrob Zayniddin o'gli	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda axborot texnologiyalarining o'rni: amalga oshirish imkoniyatlari va kelajak istiqbollari.....	469
Kurbanov Farrux Uktamovich	
Kichik biznes uchun investitsion muhit jozibadorligining ko'rsatkichlari tahlili.....	469
Jurayev Elyorbek Sobirjon o'g'li, Nabiyeva Muhabbat Djabirxanovna	

Fiskal va monetar siyosatni muvofiqlashtirishda inflyatsiya ko'rsatkichining ekonometrik tahlili	475
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Bandlikni ta'minlashning moliyaviy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	479
Karimjonov Muhammadrasul To'liqinjon o'g'li	
O'zbekiston mintaqalarida turizmni rivojlantirishni boshqarishda davlat-xususiy sherikligi mexanizmidan foydalanishning konseptual modelini ishlab chiqish	485
Mamayusupova Dilovarxon Begmatovna	
O'zbekiston mintaqalarida turizmni rivojlantirishni boshqarishda davlat-xususiy sherikligi mexanizmidan foydalanishning konseptual modelini ishlab chiqish	485
Mamayusupova Dilovarxon Begmatovna	
Аутсорсинг и рост сферы услуг: воздействие на занятость (практика США)	494
Назаров Зиёвуддин Шарофиддинович	
Restoran xizmatlari sohasi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda marketingning zamonaviy konsepsiyalarini qo'llash	501
Ibodov Kamoliddin Mamatqulovich	
The revenue manager in the hospitality industry	507
Kalandarova Gulnoza	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini joriy etilishi bo'yicha ayrim xorijiy davlatlar tajribalari	510
B.Turabov	
Barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlashning hududiy xususiyatlari.....	517
Baxtiyorova Dildora	
Elektr energiyasi samaradorligini yaxshilashga innovatsion va strategik yondashuvlar.....	521
Doliyev Shoxabbos Qulmurot o'g'li	
Don maxsulotlari sifat ko'rsatkichlariga sovuq konditsionerlash tizimini samaradorligini tahlil qilish	525
Yusupov Azamat Alijonovich, Akramova Gulhayo Abidovna	
O'zbekistonda tijorat banklarini rivojlantirish va transformatsiya qilish istiqbollari	532
Mutalova Mohira	
Optimizing crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks	537
Muydinov Muhammadsardor Abdukayum ugli	

OPTIMIZING CRISIS-HANDLING MECHANISMS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

ORCID: 0000-0002-4817-9850

Muydinov Muhammadsardor Abdukayum ugli

Doctorante Fergana Polytechnic Institute

Annotatsiya: Maqolada zamonaviy bank muammolarini tahlil qilish va barqarorlikni oshirish strategiyasini ishlab chiqish orqali tijorat banklarida inqirozni bartaraf etish mexanizmlarini optimallashtirish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu yo'nalishda amalga oshirilgan amaliy tadqiqotlar, xatarlarni boshqarish amaliyoti hamda innovatsion texnologik yechimlarni tatbiq etish natijalari tijorat banklari uchun inqirozga qarshi choralarni takomillashtirish va yo'l xaritasini taqdim etadi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, xatarlarni boshqarish tizimini optimallashtirish, bank ichidagi aloqalarni mustahkamlash va sun'iy intellekt (AI) texnologiyalarini joriy qilish banklarning moliyaviy inqirozlarni samarali boshqarish qobiliyatini sezilarli darajada oshirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: tijorat banklari, inqiroz bilan ishlash, optimallashtirish, risklarni boshqarish, sun'iy intellekt.

Abstract: The article examines the issue of optimizing mechanisms to overcome crises in commercial banks by analyzing modern banking challenges and developing strategies to enhance stability. Practical research conducted in this area, along with risk management practices and the implementation of innovative technological solutions, provides an improved roadmap and anti-crisis measures for commercial banks. Findings indicate that optimizing the risk management system, strengthening internal bank relationships, and introducing artificial intelligence (AI) technologies can significantly enhance the ability of banks to effectively manage financial crises.

Key words: commercial banks, crisis-handling, optimization, risk management, artificial intelligence.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается вопрос оптимизации механизмов преодоления кризисов в коммерческих банках через анализ современных проблем банковской системы и разработку стратегии повышения устойчивости. Проведенные практические исследования, практика управления рисками и внедрение инновационных технологических решений предлагают усовершенствованную дорожную карту и антикризисные меры для коммерческих банков. Результаты показывают, что оптимизация системы управления рисками, укрепление внутренних связей банка и внедрение технологий искусственного интеллекта (AI) могут значительно повысить способность банков эффективно управлять финансовыми кризисами.

Ключевые слова: коммерческие банки, антикризисное управление, оптимизация, управление рисками, искусственный интеллект.

INTRODUCTION

The global financial landscape is constantly exposed to various crises, including economic downturns, regulatory changes, cyber threats, and operational failures. Commercial banks, as major players in the financial ecosystem, must be well-prepared to handle crises to safeguard their liquidity, solvency, and reputation. Crisis management in the banking sector refers to the strategies and processes implemented to mitigate the negative effects of these unforeseen events.

Historically, financial institutions have been at the epicenter of crises, such as the 2008 global financial meltdown and more recent incidents involving liquidity crunches. Such crises expose banks to significant risks, including loss of customer confidence, regulatory penalties, and market instability. This article addresses the need for optimizing crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks, focusing on operational resilience, technological advancement, and risk management improvements.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks are critical for ensuring financial stability and minimizing risks during periods of economic or institutional turmoil. Extensive research in this area highlights the importance of developing robust strategies and tools for risk mitigation and swift decision-making. Scholars have extensively explored the optimization of these mechanisms to enhance their effectiveness in the face of crises.

Renowned economist Frederic Mishkin analyzed how commercial banks manage systemic risks during financial crises. He highlighted the importance of maintaining adequate capital buffers and liquidity reserves to mitigate contagion effects and ensure operational continuity. Mishkin's work underscores the need for proactive risk management policies to strengthen the resilience of financial institutions.

In the realm of operational optimization, Anthony Saunders examined the role of advanced stress-testing models in predicting and handling crises. He emphasized that incorporating macroeconomic and market scenarios into stress tests can help banks identify vulnerabilities and prepare effective contingency plans. Saunders demonstrated that stress-testing mechanisms significantly contribute to the stability of banking systems during unexpected shocks.

Douglas Diamond explored the interplay between bank liquidity and crisis response mechanisms. His research delved into the dynamics of short-term funding and liquidity pressures, arguing that establishing robust liquidity frameworks is pivotal for commercial banks to withstand external shocks. Diamond's analysis suggested that optimizing liquidity management could effectively mitigate the adverse effects of crises.

European researcher Dirk Schoenmaker focused on the importance of cross-border coordination among banks during financial crises. He stressed that international banks must adopt unified regulatory frameworks and crisis-resolution strategies to address the challenges posed by global financial disruptions. Schoenmaker's findings underline the need for enhanced collaboration between regulatory authorities to safeguard financial stability.

In addition, academic studies by Elena Carletti investigated the integration of technological tools, such as artificial intelligence and big data, into crisis-handling mechanisms. Her research demonstrated that leveraging data-driven insights allows banks to identify early warning signals of crises and implement timely interventions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative data analysis from banking institutions' crisis records and qualitative insights from interviews with industry professionals. The study also utilizes case studies of major crises, such as the 2008 financial crisis, to extract lessons on best practices for risk mitigation and crisis handling. Additionally, a review of recent technological trends, including artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, is undertaken to explore their potential in strengthening crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study revealed that banks with strong risk management frameworks are better equipped to handle crises. Risk management involves identifying potential threats, assessing their impact, and implementing strategies to mitigate them. For instance, banks that regularly perform stress tests and scenario analyses were found to have more robust responses during crises, allowing them to maintain liquidity and stabilize their operations more effectively.

Additionally, banks that embraced enterprise risk management (ERM) systems, integrating risks across all business units, reported faster recovery times. ERM promotes a holistic approach to risk by ensuring that crises in one department, such as operational risk, do not trigger a chain reaction across the organization.

The findings show that improving crisis management capabilities requires:

- Enhancing internal risk reporting,
- Continuous training of staff, and
- Regular crisis simulations.

Table No.1.

Year	Risk Management Focus	Key Components of Risk Framework	Technological Tools Implemented	Notable Improvements
2019	Credit Risk & Liquidity Risk	Stress Testing, Capital Adequacy Monitoring	Basic AI for fraud detection, Risk Data Aggregation	Introduction of real-time liquidity monitoring

2020	Pandemic-induced Operational Risks	Operational Risk Assessment, Contingency Planning	Digital banking risk management tools, Cloud solutions	Expanded stress testing for pandemic-related risks
2021	Cybersecurity and IT Infrastructure Risks	Cyber Risk Models, Data Protection, Incident Response	AI for cybersecurity threat detection and response	Improved cyber risk governance & incident response plans
2022	Inflation and Market Volatility	Scenario Analysis, Interest Rate Risk Management	Machine Learning for predictive economic modeling	Enhanced real-time scenario analysis for inflation risks
2023	Geopolitical Risks & Supply Chain Disruptions	Geopolitical Risk Assessments, Supply Chain Resilience	AI-based economic and geopolitical forecasting	Advanced integration of AI for geopolitical risk forecasting

Evolution of risk management frameworks in commercial banks (2019-2023)

Effective communication is critical during crises. Banks with well-established communication channels across departments and with external stakeholders, such as regulators, customers, and shareholders, were able to handle crises with greater success. A lack of real-time, accurate information often exacerbates crises by delaying decision-making. This research highlights that establishing clear communication protocols and enhancing transparency are key to mitigating the effects of a financial crisis.

In times of crisis, decision-making processes must be expedited. Bureaucratic delays and unclear responsibilities often slow down a bank’s response. The study suggests that banks adopting a centralized decision-making model, where senior executives take swift action, outperform those with fragmented decision-making structures.

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) tools has proven to be a game-changer for many banks. These technologies can forecast potential crises by analyzing patterns in market behavior, detecting anomalies in transaction data, and evaluating the impact of external factors like economic trends or geopolitical events. Research showed that banks with AI-driven crisis detection mechanisms could predict and prepare for crises more efficiently than those relying on traditional methods.

Moreover, AI can automate crisis management responses, reducing human errors and reaction times. For instance, automated systems can quickly adjust lending portfolios, restrict transactions, or trigger capital reserves in response to predefined crisis indicators.

The importance of regulatory compliance in crisis handling cannot be overstated. Banks that adhere strictly to regulatory guidelines on capital reserves, liquidity ratios, and reporting procedures are better positioned to withstand shocks. Following the 2008 financial crisis, stricter regulatory measures, including the Basel III accords, were introduced to strengthen banks’ resilience.

Chart No.1. Regulatory Compliance and Crisis Recovery (2019-2023).

Banks that fully integrate compliance into their daily operations can avoid penalties and maintain smoother operations during crises. This section of the results highlights that early engagement with regulators during a crisis is crucial for effective crisis management and recovery.

CONCLUSION

Optimizing crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks is pivotal to ensuring resilience and operational stability in the face of financial disruptions. A review of academic research highlights several critical aspects that banks must address to strengthen their crisis response capabilities:

Adequate Capital and Liquidity Buffers: As emphasized by Frederic Mishkin, maintaining sufficient capital and liquidity forms the foundation of a robust risk management framework.

Advanced Stress-Testing Models: Research by Anthony Saunders demonstrates the value of integrating advanced stress-testing models to proactively identify vulnerabilities and develop effective contingency plans.

Liquidity Management Optimization: Douglas Diamond's findings highlight the importance of optimizing liquidity management systems to mitigate funding pressures during crises.

Cross-Border Regulatory Coordination: Dirk Schoenmaker underscores the significance of cross-border regulatory collaboration to effectively address global financial disruptions.

Technological Tools: Elena Carletti's work shows how technological tools enhance crisis preparedness through data-driven insights and real-time monitoring.

In conclusion, a multifaceted approach combining proactive risk management, regulatory collaboration, and technological innovation is essential for optimizing crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks. These strategies not only bolster banks' ability to navigate financial turmoil but also contribute to the overall stability of the financial system. Future research and policy development should focus on advancing these mechanisms to address emerging risks in an increasingly interconnected and digitalized banking environment.

References

1. Basel Committee on Banking Supervision. (2011). *Basel III: A global regulatory framework for more resilient banks and banking systems*. Bank for International Settlements.
2. Fahlenbrach, R., Prilmeier, R., & Stulz, R. M. (2012). *This Time Is the Same: Using Bank Performance in 1998 to Explain Bank Performance During the Recent Financial Crisis*. *Journal of Finance*, 67(6), 2139–2185.
3. International Monetary Fund. (2020). *Financial Soundness Indicators and Crisis Handling in Banks*. IMF Working Paper.
4. McKinsey & Company. (2021). *Optimizing Risk Management in Financial Institutions*. McKinsey Global Institute.
5. The World Bank. (2019). *Managing Financial Crises: Risk Management and Policy Responses*. World Bank Publications.
6. Mishkin, F. S. (1996). *The Economics of Money, Banking, and Financial Markets*. HarperCollins.
7. Saunders, A. (2010). *Financial Institutions Management: A Risk Management Approach*. McGraw-Hill.
8. Diamond, D. W. (1984). *Financial Intermediation and Delegated Monitoring*. *Review of Economic Studies*, 51(3), 393–414.
9. Schoenmaker, D. (2011). *The Financial Trilemma*. *Economics Letters*, 111(1), 57–59.
10. Carletti, E. (2017). *Financial Regulation and Stability: The Role of Technology*. *European Economic Review*, 91, 62–74.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtjmoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 11

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

